

Learning new digital/computational skills to enhance your research

Template 1: A reflection template to support my growth in digital/computational research.

This template was designed for participants of the [ESCALATOR EMPOWER](#) track in 2022 to encourage intentional learning within a supportive online learning community.

Find this template online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6563415>

How to use this template:

1. Make a copy of the [Google Doc](#), download as Word or PDF document or print out - whichever you prefer.
2. Consider the tools and platforms as well as methodologies that you are currently using in your research across the research lifecycle.
3. Complete table 1 (this process may be completed over a number of months because many of the tools are not used on a daily basis and you may have forgotten that you use it at a specific stage in your research process).
4. Discuss alternative tools, platforms, and methodologies with colleagues, consider which tools, platforms and methodologies are being used in your community or research discipline. You can also browse the following resources for more information about contemporary tools:
 - a. Scholarly communication technology catalogue: <https://www.scomcat.net/>
 - b. Catalog of Open Infrastructure Services (COIs) - <https://investinopen.org/research/catalog/>
 - c. Radical Open Access - <http://radicaloa.disruptivemedia.org.uk/resources/publishing-tools/>
 - d. Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud - <https://sshopencloud.eu/service-catalogue>
5. Complete Table 2: You can continue to update this table over time as you learn about new tools, platforms and methodologies

This work was inspired by:

- <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/people-and-organizational-performance/our-insights/intentional-learning-in-practice-a-3x3x3-approach>
- <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/>

Version 1.2 May 2022

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<https://escalator.sadilar.org/champions/empower>

Hypothetical research workflows

Bosman, Jeroen; Kramer, Bianca (2016): Swiss army knives of scholarly communication - ResearchGate, Academia, Mendeley and others. figshare.

Presentation. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.4290428.v1>

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Notes

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Other templates in this series

1. Template 2: A learning path template to support my growth in digital/computational research.
EMPOWER: Templates to support learning path development for growing digital/computational research skills (v1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6563416>